

Higher education quality as a determinant to ensure state security of Ukraine

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Abstract: The article offers the authors' view on the place and role of higher education quality within the system of state safety ensuring. There is generalized the content of main approaches concerning the direct and indirect connection between a state's education system and that of security; also, there are established the directions in their contents correlation within the procedures of control system potential formation. There is established the unity and counter-apposition of interaction between the phenomena of higher education quality and state security.

Problem setting

The goal of the recently approved by the Verkhovna Rada (the parliament) of Ukraine Program of Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine has been defined as “restoring society’s trust in the state and power, construction of a competitive and investment attractive state with transparent conditions for business activities, high social standards, and service-oriented state service”. In legislators’ opinion, such steps are inseparably connected not only with fulfilling the obligations of Ukraine in the sphere of euro-integration, but also with “ensuring our state security” [1]. To the connection of the Cabinet of Ministers Program with the issues of state safety provision attests, if rather indirectly, the fact of immediate participation by representatives of the parliament’s Committee on the issues of national security, defense, and the intelligence in the procedures of development and approval of the program’s content.

The structure of the Program is set through the formulation of the mainstream goals of the government’s activities, and each of them not only can, but also should be viewed through the prism of state security determinants. Among the 17 goals of the government activities proclaimed by legislators there are some that contain a direct reference to the government activities issues, for instance, the goals set to: the Ministry of Veterans, Temporally Occupied Territories and Displaced Persons (number 5 in the general list); the Ministry of Internal Affairs (number 13 in the general list); the Ministry of Defense (number 15 in the general list); the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (number 16 in the general list). It is quite obvious that this is the activities of these ministries and other executive power bodies (services, agencies, inspections and so on) related to the circle of their professional issues that are an object of scientific research and a topic of discussion for practicing specialists. From such a perspective of scientific research as well as from judging by the composition of subjects involved in the conduction of research, one may get an impression of certain isolation of executive power bodies whose tasks are not related to national security issues. Can we really speak of the existence of direct connection between

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the goals of, say, the Ministry of Communities and Territories Development (number 10 in the general list) and the issues of immediate ensuring the national security? Before the development of sad events around the Crimea and the Donetsk and Lugansk oblasts' (areas) territories, i.e. before 2014, the answer to this question seemed more unambiguous and such that by its contextual direction tended rather to negation of the corresponding correlation. The developments in Ukraine following the events of 2014 made the society and, consequently, public management subjects not only reexamine such attitudes to national security issues, but also to state the fact of any issue of socio-political and socio-economic life being within the sphere of national security. In other words, at present there are not any directions in state policy that could be positioned beyond the sphere of national security. To prove this idea, we deem it expedient to cite the definition of the category of "national security" that is given in the Law of Ukraine "On National Security of Ukraine". In legislators' opinion, "state security is protection of state sovereignty, territorial integrity, and democratic constitutional order, and other vitally important national interests from real and potential threats of non-military character" [2]. This interpretation appeals also to protection of "vitally important national interests" which mean in this Law those of a person's, the society, and state interests "realization of which ensures state sovereignty of Ukraine, its progressive democratic development, as well as safe living conditions and well-being of its citizens". In other words, the focus of state interests' priorities are, among other things, the issues of living conditions and well-being of citizens. It is quite obvious that considering the content of this interpretation, nearly each direction in public management organs' activities should be viewed through the prism of national security.

Recent research and publications analysis

The problematics in ensuring state security, considering its significant importance for ensuring socio-political and socio-economic development of the state, is constantly within the circle of researchers' scientific interests. Among the latest scientific works, whose direction contents were focused on certain aspects of national security manifestations, and those that are worth of attention, are the researches by A. Bugaitsov (who conducted a content analysis of the notions of "security", "economic security", "social security"; viewed the category of security on the level of a person's basic needs, substantiated the theoretical foundations of state management through ensuring of economic security in Ukraine) [3], A. Datsiuk, V. Sadovsky, O. Poltorakov, R. Marutyan (who viewed the peculiarities of forming and realization of state policies of Ukraine in the period of aggression acutement; researched the algorithms of security policies formation in Europe) [4], S. Dombrovska, A. Bondarenko (who substantiated the directions to improve the contents and practices of applying state management mechanisms in state security system) [5], S. Kruk (who conducted an analysis of contents and practices of applying main normative-legal documents in the sphere of ensuring national security of Ukraine; determined the peculiarities of applying organization-and-legal state mechanism in national security management) [6], V. Pasichnyk (who viewed the approaches to interpreting the content of the category of "security" and established the peculiarities in presenting it through the prism of philosophic scientific cognizance; offered a new paradigm in national security state management) [7], V. Savitsky (who clarified the essence of national and information security; determined the threats to national and information security; substantiated the directions in state policies concerning national security ensuring) [8], G. Sytnik, V. Oluiko, M. Vavrynychuk (who viewed theoretic and methodological foundations of building up national security; disclosed the essence, forms, modes, methods, and principles of national

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safety ensuring at the current stage of Ukraine's development) [9], and by other scientists. Despite the sufficient level of scientific treatment of the problematics in state security ensuring, its separate issues still remain open for further scientific research.

Highlighting the previously unresolved sections of the general problem

Above, we have drawn attention to the fact that the measures, outlined in the Program of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, are directed, among other things, at state security ensuring, and consequently, each of the program goals determined by the government can be viewed through the prism of this problematics. Focusing attention on the first goal of the government activities (set to the Ministry of Science and Education), we have to state the fact of absence of critical amount of scientific research sufficient to substantiate the significance of education within the system of state security ensuring. The existing within scientific discourse results of the researches of the place and the role of education in state security ensuring do not, unfortunately, allow to describe this issue as having been completely solved.

Paper objective is to determine directions of improving the mechanisms of state management of higher education quality at the state level on the results of analyzing the place and the role of the phenomenon of higher education quality within the system of ensuring state security.

Paper main body

The correlation of the contents of higher education sphere with that of state / national security can be viewed through the prism of direct and indirect connections. The direct connection between the corresponding categories has its manifestation through the presence of clear references to the corresponding interdependence. For instance, the announced in 2012 by the American government report titled "The Reform of American Education and National Security" [10] accentuates directly on the connection between education and state security. Here, we certainly are aware of certain difference between the state security and the national security, but considering the fact of deep mutual penetration of one category into the other, we can presume a possibility of their conventional identity, at least within this publication. Having raised the question of the existence of cause-and-effect connections between the system of education and that of state security, the authors of the report steadfastly proved not only their presence, but also supposed the dialectic unity of the corresponding categories. Among the main threats, the cause of arising of which may be insufficient level of correspondence of education's content to challenges of time (the result of procrastination with reforming education), the authors of the report accentuate on the following: slowing down in economic growth rates and decrease in competitiveness level of national companies; a threat to citizens' physical safety (the threat to military and public safety); diminishing of the intellectual property protection level (the threat of uncontrolled proliferation of limited access information, or untrue information and (or) the one that is property of a certain subject; the threat to global interests of the USA (decrease in the cognizance level of the USA about the global world, and (or) increase in cognizance level of global world subjects about the USA); the threat to unity and solidarity of the nation. In the opinion of the authors of the report, the cause of arising and development of these threats is a gradual decline in the level and quality of education in the state. According to

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specialists' estimations, only 43% of school leavers in the USA meet the criteria (standards) set by colleges for applicants. This result, especially in the context of the fact that the level of financing American education is the highest in the world, enables to speak not only of insufficient efficiency of budget expenditures, which in itself poses a threat for state security, but also a gradual loss of human capital by the USA. Quite a significant, especially in the context of the object of our research, is one of the main conclusions of the authors of the report, namely, that a state's military potential, as well as its economic capacity for rapid development, are no longer the determining factors in ensuring its national security, for security level is formed in the realm of human capital and with its assistance. Thus, education as the primary source of human capital development becomes not only an instrument for a person and the society to amass certain knowledge and assimilate universal human values, but also a mechanism of ensuring state / national security.

Another confirmation of the fact of existence of a direct connection between the problematics of education and security is the initiative of the NATO Council concerning the establishment of a new NATO Committee on Science for Peace and Security along with the adoption of the "Science for Peace and Security" Program. This program was included into the set of "NATO documents on planning operations and exercises, Euro-Atlantic partnership work plan, the Partnership against terrorism plan, the Work plan for Mediterranean dialogue development, the NATO-Ukraine annual purpose plan, and individual partnership plans" [11]. Considering the fact that each of the mentioned documents is directly related to state safety, we may state the fact of the direct correlation between the spheres of education and security. Besides, participation of science and pedagogic workers, postgraduates, and students, provided for by the "Science for Peace and Security" Program, "will promote strengthening defense potential (gaining scientific results in such areas as chemical, biologic, and nuclear protection, telemedicine, information technologies, and so on), as well as establishing scientific partnership and qualifications improvement for Ukrainian science and pedagogic workers" [12].

The list of documents, adduced above, is not comprehensive and can be considerably extended on account not only of those containing the so-called direct reference to interdependence between education and security of a state. Let's consider the most significant of them. For instance, the content of the definition of the goal of education given by the Law of Ukraine "On Education" accentuates on: an individual's thorough development as a personality; forming values and competences; bringing up responsible citizens capable of conscious social choice; enrichment of intellectual, economic, creative, and cultural potential of Ukrainian people; ensuring stable development of Ukraine and its European choice [13]. Comparing the content of these accentuations with the given above definition of state security, we can suppose the existence of a dependency by the following directions: "protection of state sovereignty, territorial integrity and democratic constitutional order" (the Law of Ukraine "On National Security of Ukraine") vs "bringing up responsible citizens who are capable of conscious social choice" (the Law of Ukraine "On Education"); "protection [...] of vitally important national interests" (the Law of Ukraine "On National Security of Ukraine") vs "activities for the benefit of other people and society, enrichment of intellectual, economic, creative, and cultural potential of Ukrainian people on this basis" (the Law of Ukraine "On Education"). Drawing such parallels is not the focus of our attention, so we deem it possible to do with this one example.

Apart from stated above, the interdependence between education and security may be viewed within the context of separate characteristics of the latest of the mentioned

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phenomena. For instance, potential of a state that is usually considered at the level of a foundation for building up a system of national interests' protection, and, correspondently, at the level of a component of the state security system. It can be characterized, in G. Sytnik, V. Oluiko, and M. Vavrynychuk opinion, as falling into the following components: fighting, military-economic, military, demographic, spiritual-and-moral, intellectual, science-and-technological, scientific, peace, national security, deterring an aggressor, social, technological, economic, labor, export, industrial, as well as moral-and-political [9, p. 46]. The development level of each of these components of a country's potential is a product of state policy realization in the sphere of education. It is quite obvious that the source of forming and further development of "spiritual-and-moral, intellectual, science-and-technological [...] as well as moral-and political" components of a state is education. An interesting, in the context of the issue in question, is the thought of S. Mosov who, considering the potential of management system at the level of one of state management elements, views its content as a total of forces, means, knowledge, skills, and a behavior model. A similar, but not identical in its content, definition of control system potential, can be found in a research by S. Knyaz, who views this category through the unity of such elements as functions of management, organization structure of management, management personnel, management information, technical means of management, management technology, methods of management, management decisions, finances of management [14, pp. 80–82]. The stated above approaches appeal to the significance of "knowledge, skills, and a behavior model" (S. Mosov) and to "management personnel" (S. Knyaz) in control system potential. Each of these elements is a result of functioning of education system. For instance, management personnel as an element of control system potential is characterized by S. Knyaz through the prism of categories of professionalism, qualification, and education level. These categories are not only obligatory components in forming the context of state and branch standards of higher education, but also are obligatory determinants of its quality.

Conclusions of the research

In the light of the stated above, as well as our previous researches' results [15, 16], we deem it expedient to formulate the following considerations regarding the unity and opposition between the quality of higher education of a state and its security. The content of the considerations that follow relate, primarily, to the higher education system of Ukraine, though with certain approximations they can be applied to characterize the corresponding system of any country of the world.

First, the dialectics of unity between education levels and state security can be expressed through the prism of human capital, which is on the one hand a product of functioning of higher education system of a state (existing methodologies of calculating the human capital development index suppose evaluation of the level of education), while on the other hand it is positioned on the level of a component of control system potential (which in its term is viewed as a sub-system in state security). In other words, the influence of a state (public management subjects) on the components of education / higher education is an instrument of state / national security management. The level and quality of education of citizens of a country determines in the long run not only the well-being level of a person and the society (socio-economic aspect and characteristic of a society's economic sub-system), but also the level of their ability to understand the events taking place around them and to make a conscious social choice connected with acknowledgement of goals of the society along with its cultural-historic and mentality-spiritual heritage (socio-political

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aspect and characteristic of state security sub-system). The influence on an intellectually developed and patriotically educated and conscientious person by subjects with destructive attitudes towards the state order or legitimate power is quite limited. At the same time, it should be borne in mind that education, as a mechanism to pass / receive knowledge, can be used by destructive elements for actuating threats to state / national security. For instance, providing grants by foreign institutions to finance research in desired areas may considerably influence the directions of national science and education development (providing grants on humanitarian knowledge development influences indirectly the decrease in quantity and quality of research in mathematical, science, technical, and technological knowledge). Thus, education is an immediate management object on behalf of state security system of Ukraine.

Second, state policies concerning ensuring education quality, especially at the first and the second levels of higher education, can, on the one hand, enhance a raise in state / national security level (through amassing and development of control system potential and the ability of intellectually developed citizens to efficiently withstand the threats that arise), while on the other hand they can be a source of appearing and development of certain threats as well (state policies directed at raising higher education quality through decreasing the number of higher education institutions and raising requirements to applicants' knowledge, for instance through setting the minimal number (sum) of points at independent testing in one or another subject to enter a university may lead to a decrease in the level of population with higher education. A decrease in percentage of people with higher education will not only influence the human capital development level, but also will inevitably affect the ability of society to counterpart destructive influences). Besides, it should be noted that insufficient level of higher education quality becomes, on the one hand, a reason of going abroad by school-leavers with a high academic level to obtain higher education (the state loses the most competitive and motivated for development young people, which is a threat for state security, primarily for reason of national economy's losing competitiveness), and on the other hand it facilitates raising the level of providing higher education for population (decrease in higher education standards determines a raise in the level of its accessibility to so called broad strata of population, that is, nearly every school-leaver can (has a hypothetical possibility to) pass the independent evaluation tests with minimal number of points). This latter supposition is definitely somewhat contradictory, but within the context of observing the principle of all-sidedness and systemacy in analyzing security aspects in education policy, it should not be left beyond researchers' attention.

Considering the multifaceted character of manifestation and the complexity of threats and challenges in the XXI century, the stated conclusions do not exhaust the problematics of ties and connections between the systems of education and state security, but only make for development of its theoretic and methodological foundations. Among perspective directions in scientific research organizing, attention should be paid primarily to those of them, whose thematic direction is connected with substantiating the methodology of evaluating the dependency of state security level on that of quality of higher education. Besides, researchers' attention should be directed at the issues of improving the content and practices of state management mechanisms' application to ensure quality of higher education as well as stakeholders' authority in initiating and conducting reforms in the sphere of higher education.

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